

Some Novel Organosulfur Amino Acid Derivatives

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Synthesis of a series of 4-chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylamino acids (2-8), and some of the corresponding amino acid methyl esters (9-13) and hydrazides (14-16) are described. Coupling reactions of 4-chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylamino acids with amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride in THF-Et₃N medium using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide method give the dipeptide methyl esters (17-19).

Many sulfonyl derivatives process various biological activities¹. In continuation of our general program on the chemistry and reactivity of aryl sulfonyl derivatives as candidate pesticides², we report here the chlorosulfonation of 4-chlorocinnamanilide to obtain a range of novel sulfonyl derivatives for biocidal evaluation.

4-Chlorocinnamanilide reacts with chlorosulfonic acid to give an excellent yield of the corresponding sulfonyl chloride (1) according to the procedure described earlier³. Compound 1 by condensation with nucleophiles can be converted into novel sulfonyl derivatives for biological evaluation.

Results and Discussion

4-Chlorocinnamanilide was warmed with chlorosulfonic acid (12 equivalent) to give excellent yield of 4-

chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonyl chloride (1). 4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylamino acids (2-8) were prepared by the reaction of 1 with the appropriate amino acid in water-THF-Et₃N medium. The time required for completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc. THF was found to be the solvent for such coupling reactions. Compounds 2-8 were chromatographically homogeneous and did not respond to ninhydrin reaction. Complete acid hydrolysis of 4 (6 mol HCl, 24 h) followed by paper chromatography afforded ninhydrin positive spot of valine. The methyl esters (9-13) were prepared by treating the amino acid derivatives (2-8), with methanol and pure thionyl chloride at -5 to -10°. Hydrazinolysis of 9-13 in ethanol gave the corresponding hydrazides (14-16) which gave the positive benzidine and silver nitrate reactions.

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonyl dipeptide methyl esters were prepared by the carbodiimide method. Coupling of 2-8 with amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride in THF containing triethylamine and using the dicyclohexylcarbodiimide afforded the dipeptides (17-19).

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in a Griffin apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Shimadzu 440 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆, unless otherwise stated) on a Fx 90 Q FT spectrometer and mass spectra on a Shimadzu GC MS QP 1000 Ex instrument using the direct inlet system. Tlc was carried out on silica gel (Merck) plates and developed with n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1) using iodine, ninhydrin and benzidine as spraying agents.

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonyl chloride (1) was prepared (90% yield) according to the reported procedure³.

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylamino acids (2-8).
General procedure : To an amino acid (0.1 mol) in water (25 ml) and THF (15 ml) mixture, was added triethylamine (5 ml), followed by the sulfonyl chloride (1; 0.11 mol) portionwise during 30 min keeping the temperature at 10° and stirred for 2 h at 20°. Tetrahydrofuran was removed by concentration of the mixture under reduced pressure, then water (30 ml) added and acidified with 2 N HCl (congo red, pH 5). The crude products were crystallized (MeOH-H₂O) and found chromatographically homogeneous when detected with iodine and benzidine : 2, m.p. 88-90°; 3, 218-20°; 4, 237-39°; 5, 230-32°; 6, 208-10°; 7, 198-200°;

8, 220–22°; **3** and **4** ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1420, 1360 (SO₂NH), 1590 (arom C=C), 1335, 1160 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); **3** δ 0.7–0.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.2–4.6 (1H, s, CH), 4.8–5.2 (1H, s, NH), 8.20–6.70 (10H, ArH, CH=CH), 10.57 (1H, s, CONH), 10.9 (1H, s, COOH); **4** δ 2.8 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 4.2–4.6 (1H, s, CH), 4.8–5.2 (1H, s, NH), 8.10–6.80 (10H, ArH, CH=CH), 10.77 (1H, s, CONH), 10.9 (1H, s, COOH); **3** *m/z* 437 (M⁺).

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylaminomethyl esters (9-13). *General procedure* : A suspension of **2-8** (0.01 mol) in absolute methanol (150 ml) was cooled to -10° and thionyl chloride (1.2 ml) was then added dropwise during 1 h. The mixture was stirred for 3–4 h at room temperature, kept overnight, the solvent removed under reduced pressure and the residual solid was crystallized (MeOH-H₂O). The isolated methyl esters (**9-13**) were chromatographically homogeneous when developed with benzidine : **9**, m.p. 178–80°; **10**, 170–72°; **11**, 280–82°; **12**, 118–20°; **13**, 123–25°; **10** ν_{\max} 1760, 1725 (C=O), 1730 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃); **9** δ 3.4 (3H, s, OCH₃).

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonylamino acid hydrazides (14-16). *General procedure* : A mixture of **9-13** (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (85%; 0.02 mol) was stirred for 3 h at 20° and then left for 24 h at room temperature. The crystalline products (**14-16**) were washed with water and crystallized (EtOH-H₂O), and were found chromatographically homogeneous when developed with iodine and benzidine : **14**, m.p. 77–79°; **15**, 128–30°; **16**, 68–70°; ν_{\max} **14** δ 5.59 (1H, s, NH), 5.68 (2H, s, NH₂); **15** 3430, 3300 (NH, NH₂), 1550 cm⁻¹ (CONHNH₂).

4-Chlorocinnamanilide-4'-sulfonyldipeptide methyl esters (17-19). *General procedure* : To a solution of amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.016 mol) in THF (100 ml) was added triethylamine (5 ml). The solution was stirred at 20° for 30 min, cooled to 0° and sulfonylamino acid (0.008 mol) in THF (50 ml) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (1.62 g) were added. It was stirred for 2 h at 0° and for another 2 h at room temperature. Dicyclohexylurea was filtered off, acetic acid (1 ml) added, the solution left overnight, filtered and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The products (**17-19**) were crystallized (EtOH-H₂O) and found chromatographically homogeneous when detected with benzidine : **17**, m.p. 95–97°, δ 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.84 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.82 (1H, s, CONH); and other bands supporting the structure of dipeptide; **18**, 80–82°, ν_{\max} 3300, 3100 (NH, CONH), 1750 (C=O), 1320 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃); **19**, 110–12°.

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